

UDK 539.3

DOIRAVIY KO'NDALANG KESIMI O'ZGARUVCHI ELASTIK YUPQA DEVORLI QOBIQNING ERKIN BURALMA TEBRANISHI

D.Sh.Xoliqov

PhD, o'qituvchi,

X.F.Ismoilov – tayanch doktorant,

A.Ergashov – magistrant.

Samarqand davlat universiteti.

O'zbekiston.

Kirish. Fan va texnika rivojining hozirgi zamon darajasida muhandislik konstruksiyalari elementlari orasida noananaviy elementlarga talab ortib boryapti. Bunday elementlar hisobiga ko'ndalang kesimi o'zgaruvchi qobiqlarni misol qilib olish mumkin (ichki sirti silindr, tashqi sirti konussimon qobiq). Qobiqlarning tebranishlarini tadqiq qilish juda ko'p hollarda, tebranishlarning klassik nazariyalar asosida olib boriladi [1-2]. Konstruktiv elementlarning nostatsionar tebranishlari bilan bir qatorda ularning erkin tebranishlarini aniqlashtirilgan tenglamalar asosida tadqiq qilish ham muhim ahamiyatga ega [3-4]. Mazkur maqola doiraviy kesimi o'zgaruvchi qobiqning buralma tebranishlarining aniqlashtirilgan tenglamalarini keltirib chiqarishga va erkin tebranishlarini o'rganishga bag'ishlanadi.

2.Masalaning qo'yilishi. Qoiraviy kesimi o'zgaruvchi qobiqning buralma tebranishi haqidagi masalani silindrik (r, θ, z) koordinatalar sistemasida qaraymiz, qobiqning tashqi sirti simmetriya o'qiga burchak ostida joylashgani uchun bu sirtga (n, s_1, s_2) - ortogonal koordinatalarni kiritamiz va tashqi sirtga chegaraviy shartni kiritishda foydalanamiz (1-rasm). Qobiqning ichki - r_1 va tashqi - r_2 radiuslarini bo'ylama koordinataning chiziqli funksiyalari sifatida, ya'ni $r_1 = r_0$ va $r_2 = r_0 + h + fz$ ko'rinishida tanlaymiz. Bu yerda $r_0 = const$, h - qobiq qalinligi, $f = tg\varphi$

1-Rasm. Doiraviy ko'ndalang kesimi o'zgaruvchi aobianussimon aobia.

Qaralayotgan masalada buralma tebranish o'qqa nisbatan simmetrik bo'lganligi uchun, masala θ - burchakning o'zgarishidan bog'liq emas, shuning uchun faqat $U_\theta(r, z, t)$ buralma ko'chish noldan farqli va

$$U_\theta = U_\theta(r, z, t) \quad (1)$$

Kuchlanishlarni U_θ - orqali quyidagi ko'rinishda yozamiz

$$M \sigma_{r\theta} = \mu \left[\frac{1}{r} - \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right] U_\theta; \quad \sigma_{z\theta} = -\mu \frac{\partial U_\theta}{\partial z} \quad (2)$$

bu yerda μ - Lamé koeffitsienti.

Harakat tenglamalarini silindrik koordinatalar sistemasida buralma tebranish uchun quyidagicha tavsiflaymiz:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + 2 \frac{\sigma_{r\theta}}{r} = \rho \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_\theta}{\partial t^2} \right), \quad (3)$$

bu yerda ρ - qobiq materialining zichligi.

Agar konussimon qobiqning buralma tebranishlari uning ichki radiusi $r_1 = r_0$ bo'lgan ichki sirtiga ta'sir etuvchi - $f_{r\theta}^{(1)}(z, t)$ va tashqi radiusi $r_2 = r_0 + h + fz$ bo'lgan tashqi sirtiga ta'sir etuvchi - $f_{ns_1}^{(2)}(z, t)$ tashqi kuchlar ta'siridan yuzaga kelsa, quyidagi chegaraviy shartlar o'rinli bo'ladi:

a). ($r = r_1$) da

$$\sigma_{r\theta} = f_{r\theta}(z, t), \quad \sigma_{z\theta} = 0 \quad (4)$$

b). ($r = r_2$) da

$$\sigma_{r\theta} - f \sigma_{z\theta} = \Delta_0 f_{ns_1}(z, t), \quad \Delta_0 = 1 + f^2. \quad (5)$$

Boshlang'ich shartlar nolga teng, yani $t = 0$ bo'lganda $U_\theta = \frac{\partial U_\theta}{\partial t} = 0$

3. Elastik konussimon qobiqning buralma tebranishi:

Qobiq harakat tenglamasi (3) ga ko'chishning (1) va kuchlanishlarning (2) ifodasini qo'ssak, soddalashtirishlardan so'ng quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\frac{\partial^2 U_\theta}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial U_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 U_\theta}{\partial z^2} - \frac{U_\theta}{r^2} = \frac{\rho}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 U_\theta}{\partial t^2} \quad (6)$$

Bu yerda U_θ - buralma tebranish, $\sigma_{r\theta}, \sigma_{z\theta}$ - kuchlanish va $f_{r\theta}(z, t), f_{ns_1}(z, t)$ tashqi yuklar funksiyani (7) ko'rinishda almashtiramiz.

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_{\theta}(r, z, t) &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin qz}{-\cos qz} \left. \right\} dq \int_{(t)} U_{\theta}^{(0)}(r, q, p) e^{pt} dp \\
 [\sigma_{r\theta}, \sigma_{z\theta}](r, z, t) &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin qz}{-\cos qz} \left. \right\} dq \int_{(t)} [\sigma_{r\theta}^{(0)}, \sigma_{z\theta}^{(0)}](r, q, p) e^{pt} dp \\
 [f_{r\theta}, f_{ns_1}](z, t) &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin qz}{-\cos qz} \left. \right\} dq \int_{(t)} [f_{r\theta}^{(0)}, f_{ns_1}^{(0)}](z, t) e^{pt} dp
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

(7) ifodani (6) ifodaga qo'yish orqali quyidagini hosil qilamiz

$$\Delta_{\beta} U_{\theta}^{(0)}(r, q, p) = 0 \tag{8}$$

bu yerda $\Delta_{\beta} = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \left(\beta^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} \right)$, $\beta^2 = \frac{1}{b^2} p^2 - q^2$, $b^2 = \frac{\mu}{\rho}$, ρ - qobiq

materialining zichligi;

(8) tenglamaning $r=0$ va $r \rightarrow \infty$ bo'lganda chegaralangan umumiy yechimi

$$U_{\theta}^{(0)}(r, q, p) = C_1 I_1(\beta r) + C_2 K_1(\beta r) \tag{9}$$

bo'ladi. Bunda $I_1(\beta r)$ va $K_1(\beta r)$ - modifitsirlangan Bessel funksiyalari, $C_1(q, p)$ va $C_2(q, p)$ - ixtiyoriy integrallash o'zgarmlari.

Qobiq nuqtalarining buralma ko'chishi $U_{\theta}^{(0)}(r, q, p)$ tasvirini r - radial koordinata bo'yicha darajali qatorga yoyamiz. Bir qancha matematik almashtirishlardan so'ng, almashtirilgan $U_{\theta}^{(0)}$ ko'chishning $U_{\theta,0}^{(0)}$ va $U_{\theta,1}^{(0)}$ belgilashlari orqali quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$U_{\theta}^{(0)}(r, p, q) = 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(r/2)^{2n+1}}{n!(n+1)!} \beta^{2n} U_{\theta,0}^{(0)} + \xi \left(\frac{1}{r} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \eta_{1,n}(r) \frac{(r/2)^{2n+1}}{n!(n+1)!} \beta^{2n+2} \right) U_{\theta,1}^{(0)}. \tag{10}$$

Bu ifoda uchun (7) integral almashtirishiga o'hshash p va q parametrlar bo'yicha quyidagi teskari almashtirishlarni va $\lambda^n(\zeta)$ -differensial operatorlarni qo'llasak,

$$[U_{\theta,0}, U_{\theta,1}] = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin qz}{-\cos qz} \left. \right\} dq \int_{(t)} [U_{\theta,0}^{(0)}, U_{\theta,1}^{(0)}](r, q, p) e^{pt} dp, \quad \lambda^n(\zeta) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin qz}{-\cos qz} \left. \right\} dq \int_{(t)} \beta^{2n}(\zeta) e^{pt} dp$$

U holda

$$U_{\theta}(r, z, t) = \frac{\xi}{r} U_{\theta,1} + 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \lambda^n U_{\theta,0} \frac{(r/2)^{2n+1}}{n!(n+1)!} + \xi \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \eta_{1,n}(r) \lambda^{n+1} U_{\theta,1} \frac{(r/2)^{2n+1}}{n!(n+1)!}. \tag{11}$$

ifodalarga ega bo'lamiz.

Agar (11) formulada $n=1$ bo'lgan hol bilan chegaralanilsa konussimon qatlamning ixtiyoriy kesimi nuqtalari uchun ko'chish ifodasini hosil qilamiz:

$$U_{\theta}(r, z, t) = r \left[U_{\theta,0} + \frac{\xi}{r^2} U_{\theta,1} + \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \ln \frac{r}{\xi} \right) \lambda U_{\theta,1} \right] + \frac{r^3}{4} \lambda U_{\theta,0} + \frac{\xi r^3}{64} \eta_{1,1}(r) \lambda^2 U_{\theta,1}, \tag{12}$$

Ko‘chishning (12) ifodasini orqali aniqlangan (2) kuchlanish ifodalarini (4) va (5) chegaraviy shartlarga qo‘yamiz:

$$\frac{r_1^2}{4} \lambda U_{\theta,0} + \xi \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\lambda - \frac{4}{r_1^2} \right) + \frac{r_1^2}{8} \left(\ln \frac{r_1}{\xi} - \frac{1}{4} \right) \lambda^2 \right] U_{\theta,1} = \mu f_{r\theta}^i(z,t) \quad (13)$$

$$\left[\frac{r_2^2}{4} \lambda - fr_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right] U_{\theta,0} + \xi \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\lambda - \frac{4}{r_2^2} - \frac{2f}{r_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) - \frac{r_2^2}{32} \lambda^2 + \frac{r_2}{2} \left(\frac{r_2}{4} \lambda^2 - \lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \ln \frac{r_2}{\xi} \right] U_{\theta,1} = \mu(1+f^2) f_{ns_1}^i(z,t)$$

Agar $\beta^2 = \frac{1}{b^2} p^2 - q^2$ va $\lambda^n = \left[\frac{\rho}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right]^n, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ operatorlari (z,t)

o‘zgaruvchilar uchun, natijaviy (13) tenglamalar sistemasida hisobga olsak, doiraviy kesimi o‘zgaruvchi qobiq buralma tebranishining umumiy differensial tenglamalar sistemasidan iborat bo‘ladi. Bu tenglamalar sistemasining tartibi cheksiz katta bo‘lganligidan, uni amaliy masalalarni yechishda qo‘llab bo‘lmaydi. Shuning uchun (13) tenglamalar sistemasida $n = 0$ bo‘lgan hol bilan chegaralanib, qobiqning ichki va tashqi sirtiga hech qanday tashqi kuch ta’sir qilmayapti yani $f_{r\theta}(z,t) = 0$ va $f_{ns_1}(z,t) = 0$

deb hisoblab, qobiqning qalinligi yetarli darajada kichik holda $\ln \frac{r_i}{\xi} \rightarrow 0$ teng deb

olamiz natijaviy quyidagi ikkinchi tartibli bir jinsli differensial tenglamalar sistemasiga kelamiz

$$\frac{r_1^2}{4} \left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) U_{\theta,0} + \xi \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{4}{r_1^2} \right) \right] U_{\theta,1} = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$\left[\frac{r_2^2}{4} \left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) - fr_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right] U_{\theta,0} + \xi \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{4}{r_2^2} - \frac{2f}{r_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \right] U_{\theta,1} = 0$$

Bu aniqlangan (14) sistema ko‘ndalang kesimi o‘zgaruvchi elastik yupqa devorli qobiqning buralma tebranish tenglamasidir.

4. Xulosa: Biz qarayotgan masalada, yupqa devorli qobiqning simmetriya o‘qi bo‘ylab yo‘nalgan z-koordinataning boshlang‘ich nuqtasidagi radiusi va qobiq uzunligi l -masofadagi radiuslari yupqa devorli qobiq bo‘lish sharti, ya’ni $h/R < 0.1$ (R -qobiq o‘rta sirtining radiusi) bo‘lishini ta’minlash kerak bo‘ladi. Bu esa qobiq uzunligini – l va “hujum burchagi” – φ larni tanlashga bog‘liq bo‘ladi.

REFERENCES

1. K. Khudoynazarov, J. Abdurazakov, D. Kholikov Nonlinear torsional vibrations of a circular cylindrical elastik shell // *International Scientific Conference on Actual Problems of Applied Mechanics - APAM-2021*. October 27-29, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0118844>

2. X. Худайназаров Продольный удар по круговой цилиндрической вязко-упругой оболочке. // Изв. АН УзССР. Сер. Техн. науки. -1990. №3. 31-37.
3. Xoliqov D.Sh., Abdurazzaqov J.N., Xudoynazarova D.X. Free torsional vibrations of a round elastik cone-shaped rod. Ilmiy axborotnoma SamDU. 2021. №1(125). 94-100 –b.
4. Абдураззаков Ж., Холиков Д., Худойназаров Х. Задачи осесимметричных нелинейных колебаний круговых цилиндрических оболочек и стержней // Проблемы архитектуры и строительства (научно-технический журнал- 2019, № 4. С.134-136.